

IPBES TCA Chapter 1. Knowledge gaps analysis / IPBES transformative change assessment

Code: IPBES_TCA_1.6_07_2024

Versioning 01: 14.06.2024

Versioning 02: 23.07.2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11657378>

Project leader:

Esther Turnhout (e.turnhout@utwente.nl)

Researcher:

Rainer Krug (rainer@krugs.de)

Data curator:

Anouk Renaud (anouk.renaud@umontpellier.fr)

Description:

The IPBES scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 1 should include a presentation of knowledge gaps. The section 1.5 includes general information on this. In this context, a literature review has been conducted to verify the identified knowledge gaps.

Process overview

Protocol

Throughout literature review and analysis, assessment experts identified a number of knowledge gaps in their assessment on transformative change and the underlying causes of biodiversity loss. The lead expert of this data management report, with the support of the IPBES data management task force, used the transformative change assessment corpus of literature to verify the identified knowledge gaps in chapter 1.

1. To gain an understanding of the relative importance of policy-oriented work on biodiversity assessment experts, there was a search based on a part of the transformative change assessment corpus of literature: the NATURE corpus (consisting of 26,165,986 works) for the following search terms in CONCEPTS_1:

conservation OR management OR policy OR governance.

This resulted in 3,753,713 works (2.1) which is **14,35%** of the NATURE corpus.

2. To have an understanding of the relative importance of relation concepts of nature and biodiversity that go beyond natural science understandings, a search has been made in the NATURE corpus for the following search terms in CONCEPTS_2:

Holistic OR Integrative OR connectedness OR reciprocal OR reciprocity OR care OR caring OR stewardship OR respect OR “mother earth” OR “Mother Nature” OR “biocultural diversity” OR “nature culture” OR “nature-culture” OR socionatures OR socio-natures OR relational OR non-human OR “non-human” OR “beyond human” OR “more than human” OR cohabitation OR convivial OR conviviality OR “relational values” OR harmony.

This resulted in 2,624,983 works (2.2) which is **10,03%** of the NATURE corpus.

3. The overlap between these two, so works that include both the first search string and the second results in 675,412 works (2.3) which is **2,58%** of the NATURE corpus.

From this, it has been concluded that these themes are underrepresented in literature. The assessment experts note that policy or management-oriented work in the domain of nature also does not seem to include broader notions of nature and biodiversity and vice versa, work that does discuss these broader notions, does not refer to policy and management. This suggests that most work on nature focuses on natural sciences and on natural science concept.